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Abstract:

This article highlights the scope of the integrations extends to Data & Systems integration and explains why it requires the incorporation of both technical and non-technical domains. This paper explores the essentials of integration and lays a theoretical foundation for the integration of systems using cloud and on-premises. It reviews its definition, players, detailed info on issues that are expected to be addressed and effective solutions. It will introduce Safety Cube theory to outline these fundamental aspects of Data & system integration. Example applications are provided at the end of the paper.

Key words- Integration, API, security, cloud, on-premises, Decryption and encryption, two-factor authentications.

Introduction:

Whether it is on-premises or cloud integration depends on how well you define the process can be able to get all of your data together in one place. Interface will enable you to achieve this.

Interfaces are becoming not expensive and user friendly to design with the available advanced tools and software's coming in the computer industry. They can decrease a decent portion of the cost of any system implementation project.

Managing integrity between multiple data sources are becoming easy and effective now adays with cloud computing solutions. There will most likely be Realtime, transactional transactions during the integration.

Replications, fetching information between systems are using with cloud platforms need to elaborate.

Simple Architecture:

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Description and Players:

Integration of Data using cloud and on-premises platform benefits not only customers but the health of the business. This is an improvement compared to performance depending on product line. These results are the combined result of the heroic effort and scalable processes.

Today, Integration solutions focused teams are divided into many divisions: Reactive Support, Product Support, and Easy solutions.

Deployment Models in cloud:

- **Public Cloud (or External Cloud):** In this model, computing resources are dynamically provisioned over the Internet via Web applications or Web services from trusted third party provider. Public clouds are run by third parties, and applications from different customers are likely to be mixed together on the cloud's servers, storage systems, and networks. Although the public cloud has compelling advantages, there existing the hidden risk of security, regulatory policy compliance and quality of service (QoS) requirements.
- **Private Cloud (or Internal Cloud):** In the private cloud deployment, computing resources are used and controlled by a private enterprise. It is generally deployed in the enterprises data center and managed by internal personnel or service provider. The main advantage of this model is that the security, compliance, and QoS are under the control of the enterprises [7].
- **Hybrid Cloud (or Mixed Cloud):** The Hybrid Cloud environment intersects and combines multiple public and private cloud models. It enables the enterprise applications to running state-steady workload in the private cloud and requesting the public cloud for intensive computing resources when peak workload occurs. Hybrid clouds introduce the complexity of determining how to distribute applications across both a public and private cloud.
- **Community Cloud (or Group Cloud):** In this Community deployment model several organizations jointly construct and share cloud infrastructure as well as policies, requirements, values, and concerns. The cloud community forms into a degree of economic scalability and democratic equilibrium. The cloud infrastructure could be hosted by a third-party vendor or within one of the organization in the community. This is emerging cloud used by many social networking website like facebook, orkut, etc.

Integration team is critical to the success of any company, especially high demanded sectors. Cloud hosting services maintains retention record, which can be anywhere for comparable products.

API -APIs are the foundation of digital transformation. Whether developing applications in cloud-native and serverless architectures or providing a backend for applications, APIs enable the exchange of data and communication between applications and databases.

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Example:

Uses integration (Cloud or On-premises):

- Effective and Productive Technology infrastructure
- Easy to integrate with maximum efficiency and flexibility.
- Maintenance of software and hardware.
- Cost effective.

Integrations Issues and Reasons:

Motivated attackers are increasingly targeting Data, Systems or APIs as the pathway to their target's underlying infrastructure and database, there might be a critical threat to an organization's sensitive data. What's more, security teams don't often have visibility into the Interfaces, APIs that technical teams are creating or deploying, making them a dangerous blindspot.

Integration or API Security empowers customers to protect critical applications and infrastructure from online fraud, API abuses, DDoS attacks, and more.

It is required that API Security should automatically detect API endpoints to enable comprehensive API visibility for security teams. There should not be manual intervention to creation of a positive security model.

Security uniquely solves two significant challenges that every business faces today: protecting the APIs that enable innovation, while monitoring and securing the underlying data. This differentiated ability brings to life of protecting data and all paths to it.

Integration and API Security bridges the gap between the domains by providing holistic visibility in a SaaS that can be quickly deployed in any environment.

If organizations overcome security issues will be a significant achievement that paves the way for a new standard in security SaaS products to deliver value beyond the security team, and enable secure innovation within the development lifecycle.

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Security during integration:

Several functionalities would help to eradicate data silos by having a centralized interface of information to improve processes and workflows.

There are multiple data touch points that need to be assessed and monitored from a security and compliance perspective.

Some of the key areas are:

- Cyber intelligence discovery
- Monitoring and vulnerability assessment
- Assets level monitoring
- Network monitoring

Best Security options for data during integration are using encryption /decryption and two factor authentication.

Decryption /Encryption: There are lot of unique code decrypter and encrypt tool available which helps to decrypt or encrypt data with different encryption algorithms.

Two-Factor Authentication (TOTP) is a process where a user is prompted during the sign-in process with password for an additional form of identification. The Authenticator applications displays the time-based, one-time passwords (TOTP) helps to safeguard access to data and applications of the target system while maintaining password login users. It acts as an extra layer of security check to verify a user's identity by requiring a second form of authentication. You can also use many authenticators such as Microsoft, SAP or Google Authenticator.

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SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Companies should try to develop self sufficient integration services of their own with absolute safety and security measurements at data. Various functionalities are available to design and facilitate integration with new as well as existing applications and systems. The main purpose of this document is to understand features, issues and availability of best solutions related to Data and System integrations. Overall, the integration area hosted applications produced incredible results throughout the years. The Integration technology increased customer satisfaction in the face of a massive organizational overhaul.